

EVEN HAMMING DISTANCE LABELING OF SNAKE GRAPHS

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Abstract

A function $f:V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ is said to be even hamming distance labeling if there exist an induced function $f^*:E \rightarrow \{2,4,6,\dots,n\}$ such that for every $uv \in E$, $f^*(uv) = hd([f(u)]_2, [f(v)]_2)$ satisfies the following conditions: (i) For every vertex $v \in V$, the set of all edges incident with v receive distinct even numbers as labels. (ii) For every edge $e = uv$, the adjacent vertices u and v receive distinct labels. The even hamming distance number of a graph G is defined as the least positive integer n such that $2^n - 1 \geq k$, where $k = \max\{f(v)/v \in V\}$ and is denoted by $\eta''_{hd}(G)$. In this paper we obtain the even hamming distance number of Triangular Snake graph, Alternate Triangular Snake, Quadrilateral Snake and Alternate Quadrilateral Snake.

Keywords: Even Hamming Distance Labeling, Even Hamming Distance Number, Triangular Snake Graph, Alternate Triangular Snake, Quadrilateral Snake and Alternate Quadrilateral Snake.

1. INTRODUCTION

A vertex labeling of a graph G is an assignment f of labels to the vertices of G that induces a label for every edge uv depending on the vertex labels $f(u)$ and $f(v)$ [1]. we introduced the concept of hamming distance labeling, odd hamming distance labeling and even hamming distance labeling. It has been proved that some Path related graphs admit hamming distance [2] and odd hamming distance labeling [3] and some cycle related graphs admit even hamming distance labeling [4]. In this paper, we show that some Snake related graphs admit even hamming distance labeling and their even hamming distance number were obtained. Here the Triangular Snake T_m is obtained from the Path P_m by replacing each edge of a Path by a Triangle C_3 [6]. An Alternate Triangular Snake $A(T_m)$ is obtained from a Path P_m in which every alternate edge is replaced by C_3 . A Quadrilateral Snake Q_m is obtained from a Path P_m by replacing each edge of P_m by a Cycle C_4 and Alternate Quadrilateral Snake $A(Q_m)$ is obtained from a Path P_m , in which each alternate edge of P_m is replaced by a Cycle [5].

2. EVEN HAMMING DISTANCE LABELLING OF SOME SNAKE GRAPHS

Theorem 2.1. The Triangular Snake graph T_m , $m \geq 2$, is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(T_m) = 8$.

Proof: Let us consider the Triangular Snake graph T_m with vertex set $V = \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq 2m\}$ and edge set $E = \{\{v_i v_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq 2m - 1\} \cup \{v_0 v_2\} \cup \{v_{2i} v_{2i+2} / 1 \leq i \leq m - 1\}\}$. Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of T_m in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for vertex labeling are explained in the following algorithm.

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Triangular Snake graph T_m .

Input: Triangular Snake graph.

$V \leftarrow \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq 2m\}$

$v_0 \leftarrow 1; v_1 \leftarrow 62;$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$v_{2i} \leftarrow \begin{cases} 13 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \\ 242 & \text{if } i \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4) \\ 2 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \\ 253 & \text{if } i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 4) \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 1$ to $m - 1$ do

$$v_{2i+1} \leftarrow \begin{cases} 50 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \\ 1 & \text{if } i \equiv 2,0(\text{mod } 4) \\ 61 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \end{cases}$$

end for

end procedure

Output: The labeled vertices of T_m graph.

The induced function $f^*: E \rightarrow \{2,4,6, \dots, n\}$ for the given function f is defined by $f^*(uv) = hd([f(u)]_2, [f(v)]_2)$, where $uv \in E$. Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

$$f^*(v_0 v_2) = hd([f(v_0)]_2, [f(v_2)]_2) = 2; f^*(v_0 v_1) = hd([f(v_0)]_2, [f(v_1)]_2) = 6.$$

$$f^*(v_1 v_2) = hd([f(v_1)]_2, [f(v_2)]_2) = 4.$$

For $2 \leq i \leq 2m - 1$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2); f^*(v_i v_{i+1}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(v_{i+1})]_2) = 6.$

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2); f^*(v_i v_{i+1}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(v_{i+1})]_2) = 2.$

For $1 \leq i \leq m - 1$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 1 \pmod{2}; f^*(v_{2i}v_{2(i)+2}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(v_{2(i)+2})]_2) = 8$.

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 0 \pmod{2}; f^*(v_{2i}v_{2(i)+2}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(v_{2(i)+2})]_2) = 4$.

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct even numbers as labels. Hence the Triangular Snake graph T_m , admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(T_m) = 8, m \geq 2$.

Figure 1: Even Hamming Distance Labeled T_5 graph

Theorem 2.2. The Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$, $m \geq 2$, is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(T_m)) = 8$, where m is a positive odd integer and the triangle starts from the first vertex.

Proof: Let us consider the Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$ with vertex set $V = \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor\}$ and edge set $E = \{u_i u_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup \{u_{2i} v_{\frac{2i}{2}} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor\} \cup \{v_i u_{2i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor\}$. Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of $A(T_m)$ in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for vertex labeling are explained in the following algorithm.

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$.

Input: Alternate Triangular Snake graph.

$$V \leftarrow \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor\} \right\}$$

$$u_0 \leftarrow 1; v_0 \leftarrow 62;$$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$u_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 13 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod}4) \\ 242 & \text{if } i \equiv 2(\text{mod}4) \\ 2 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod}4) \\ 253 & \text{if } i \equiv 0(\text{mod}4) \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 1$ to $\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor$ do

$v_i \leftarrow 1$

end for

end procedure

Output: The labeled vertices of $A(T_m)$ graph.

Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_0u_1) = hd([f(u_0)]_2, [f(u_1)]_2) = 2; f^*(v_0u_1) = hd([f(v_0)]_2, [f(u_1)]_2) = 4.$$

$$\text{For } i = 0 \text{ to } \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor; f^*(u_{2i}v_{\frac{2i}{2}}) = hd([f(u_{2i})]_2, [f(v_{\frac{2i}{2}})]_2) = 6.$$

$$\text{For } i = 1 \text{ to } \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor \text{ do}; f^*(v_iu_{2i+1}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(u_{2i+1})]_2) = 2.$$

For $i = 1$ to $m-1$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 1(\text{mod}2); f^*(u_iu_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 8.$

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 0(\text{mod}2); f^*(u_iu_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 4.$

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct even numbers as labels. Hence the Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$, admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(T_m)) = 8, m \geq 2.$

Figure 2: Even Hamming Distance Labeled $A(T_5)$ graph

Theorem 2.3. The Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m), m \geq 2,$ is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(T_m)) = 8,$ where m is a positive even integer and the Triangle starts from the first vertex.

Proof: Let us consider the Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$ with vertex set $V = \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \left\{ v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2} - 1 \right\} \right\}$ and edge set $E = \left\{ \{u_i u_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup \left\{ u_{2i} v_{\frac{2i}{2}} / 0 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2} - 1 \right\} \cup \left\{ v_i u_{2i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2} - 1 \right\} \right\}$. Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of $A(T_m)$ in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for labeling the vertices are explained in the following algorithm.

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$.

Input: Alternate Triangular Snake graph.

$$V \leftarrow \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \left\{ v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \frac{m}{2} - 1 \right\} \right\}$$

$$u_0 \leftarrow 1; v_0 \leftarrow 62;$$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$u_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 13 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod}4) \\ 242 & \text{if } i \equiv 2(\text{mod}4) \\ 2 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod}4) \\ 253 & \text{if } i \equiv 0(\text{mod}4) \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 1$ to $\frac{m}{2} - 1$ do

$$v_i \leftarrow 1$$

end for

end procedure

output: The labeled vertices of $A(T_m)$ graph.

Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_0 u_1) = hd([f(u_0)]_2, [f(u_1)]_2) = 2; f^*(v_0 u_1) = hd([f(v_0)]_2, [f(u_1)]_2) = 4.$$

$$\text{For } i = 1 \text{ to } \frac{m}{2} - 1; f^*(v_i u_{2i+1}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(u_{2i+1})]_2) = 2.$$

$$\text{For } i = 0 \text{ to } \frac{m}{2} - 1; f^*(u_{2i} v_{\frac{2i}{2}}) = hd([f(u_{2i})]_2, [f(v_{\frac{2i}{2}})]_2) = 6.$$

For $i = 1$ to $m-1$

$$\text{Case (i): If } i \equiv 1(\text{mod}2); f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 8.$$

$$\text{Case (ii): If } i \equiv 0(\text{mod}2); f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 4.$$

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct even numbers as labels. Hence the Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$, admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(T_m)) = 8, m \geq 2$.

Figure 3: Even Hamming Distance Labeled $A(T_6)$ graph

Theorem 2.4. The Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$, $m \geq 2$, is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(T_m)) = 8$, where m is a positive integer and the triangle starts from the second vertex.

Proof: Let us consider the Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$ with vertex set $V = \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\}$ and edgeset $E = \{u_i u_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup \{u_{2i+1} v_{\lfloor \frac{2(i+1)}{2} \rfloor} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \cup \{v_i u_{2i+2} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\}$. Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of $A(T_m)$ in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for vertex labeling are explained in the following algorithm.

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$.

Input: Alternate Triangular Snake graph.

$$V \leftarrow \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\}$$

$$u_0 \leftarrow 1;$$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$u_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 13 & \text{if } i \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ 242 & \text{if } i \equiv 2 \pmod{4} \\ 2 & \text{if } i \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \\ 253 & \text{if } i \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 0$ to $\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1$

$$v_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 50 & \text{if } i \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ 61 & \text{if } i \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

end for

end procedure

Output: The labeled vertices of $A(T_m)$ graph.

Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

$$f^*(u_0u_1) = hd([f(u_0)]_2, [f(u_1)]_2) = 2.$$

$$\text{For } i = 0 \text{ to } \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1; f^*(u_{2(i)+1}v_{\lfloor \frac{2(i)+1}{2} \rfloor}) = hd([f(u_{2(i)+1})]_2, [f(v_{\lfloor \frac{2(i)+1}{2} \rfloor})]_2) = 6.$$

$$f^*(v_i u_{2i+2}) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(u_{2i+2})]_2) = 2.$$

For $i = 1$ to $m-1$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 1 \pmod{2}; f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 8.$

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 0 \pmod{2}; f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 4.$

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct even numbers as labels. Hence the Alternate Triangular Snake graph $A(T_m)$, admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(T_m)) = 8, m \geq 2.$

Figure 4: Even Hamming Distance Labeled $A(T_6)$ graph

Theorem 2.5. The Quadrilateral Snake graph $Q_m, m \geq 2$ is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(Q_m) = 8.$

Proof: Let us consider the Quadrilateral Snake graph Q_m with vertex set

$$V = \{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i, w_i / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \} \quad \text{and edge set}$$

$E = \{ \{u_i u_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup \{u_i v_i / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup \{u_i w_{i-1} / 1 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i w_i / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \}.$ Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of Q_m in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for labeling the vertices are explained in the following algorithm.

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Quadrilateral Snake graph $Q_m.$

Input: Quadrilateral Snake graph.

$$V \leftarrow \{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i, w_i / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \}$$

$u_0 \leftarrow 0; v_0 \leftarrow 15; w_0 \leftarrow 48;$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$u_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \\ 60 & \text{if } i \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4) \\ 12 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \\ 51 & \text{if } i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 4) \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 1$ to $m - 1$ do

$$v_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 252 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \\ 0 & \text{if } i \equiv 0,2(\text{mod } 4) \\ 243 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \end{cases} ; w_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 195 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \\ 63 & \text{if } i \equiv 0,2(\text{mod } 4) \\ 204 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \end{cases}$$

end for

end procedure

Output: The labeled vertices of Q_m graph.

Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

For $0 \leq i \leq m - 1, f^*(v_i w_i) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(w_i)]_2) = 6.$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2)$

$f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 2 ; f^*(u_i v_i) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(v_i)]_2) = 4$

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2)$

$f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 6 ; f^*(u_i v_i) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(v_i)]_2) = 8$

For $1 \leq i \leq m$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2); f^*(u_i w_{i-1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(w_{i-1})]_2) = 4$

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2); f^*(u_i w_{i-1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(w_{i-1})]_2) = 8$

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct even numbers as labels. Hence the Quadrilateral Snake graph Q_m , admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(Q_m) = 8, m \geq 2.$

Figure 5: Even Hamming Distance Labeled $A(T_6)$ graph

Theorem 2.6. The Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m)$, $m \geq 2$, is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(Q_m)) = 6$, where Q_m starts from the first vertex.

Proof: Let us consider the Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m)$ with vertex set $V = \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \left\{ v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\} \cup \left\{ w_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\}$ and edge set $E = \left\{ \{u_i u_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq m-1\} \cup \left\{ u_{2i} v_{\frac{2(i)}{2}} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\} \cup \left\{ v_i w_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\} \cup \left\{ w_i u_{2i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\}$. Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of $A(Q_m)$ in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for labeling the vertices are explained in the following algorithm

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m)$.

Input: Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph.

$$V \leftarrow \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \left\{ v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\} \cup \left\{ w_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \right\} \right\}$$

$$u_0 \leftarrow 0; v_0 \leftarrow 15; w_0 \leftarrow 48;$$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$u_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 4) \\ 60 & \text{if } i \equiv 2(\text{mod } 4) \\ 12 & \text{if } i \equiv 3(\text{mod } 4) \\ 51 & \text{if } i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 4) \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 1$ to $\lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \rfloor$ do

$$v_i \leftarrow 0; w_i \leftarrow 63;$$

end for

end procedure

output: The labeled vertices of $A(Q_m)$ graph.

Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

For $i = 0$ to $m-1$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2)$; $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 2$.

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2)$; $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 6$.

For $i = 0$ to $\lfloor \frac{m-1}{2} \rfloor$; $f^*(u_{2i} v_{\frac{2(i)}{2}}) = hd([f(u_{2i})]_2, [f(v_{\frac{2(i)}{2}})]_2) = 4$

$$f^*(v_i w_i) = hd([f(v_i)]_2, [f(w_i)]_2) = 6; f^*(w_i u_{2i+1}) = hd([f(w_i)]_2, [f(u_{2i+1})]_2) = 4$$

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct labels. Hence the alternate quadrilateral snake graph $A(Q_m)$, admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(Q_m)) = 6, m \geq 2$.

Figure 6: Even Hamming Distance Labeled $A(T_5)$ graph

Theorem 2.7. The Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m), m \geq 2$ is an even hamming distance labeled graph and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(Q_m)) = 6$, where Q_m starts from the second vertex.

Proof: Let us consider the Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m)$ with vertex set

$$V = \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \cup \{w_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \right\} \text{ and edge set}$$

$E = \left\{ \{u_i u_{i+1} / 0 \leq i \leq m - 1\} \cup \{u_{2i+1} v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \cup \{v_i w_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \cup \{w_i u_{2i+2} / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \right\}$. Define a function $f: V \rightarrow N \cup \{0\}$ to label the vertices of $A(Q_m)$ in such a way that $f(u) \neq f(v)$ for any two adjacent vertices and the procedure for labeling the vertices are explained in the following algorithm

Procedure: Vertex labeling of Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m)$.

Input: Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph.

$$V \leftarrow \left\{ \{u_i / 0 \leq i \leq m\} \cup \{v_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \cup \{w_i / 0 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1\} \right\}$$

$$u_0 \leftarrow 0;$$

for $i = 1$ to m do

$$u_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 3 & \text{if } i \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ 60 & \text{if } i \equiv 2 \pmod{4} \\ 12 & \text{if } i \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \\ 51 & \text{if } i \equiv 0 \pmod{4} \end{cases}$$

end for

for $i = 0$ to $\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1$ do

$$w_i \leftarrow 0;$$

$$v_i \leftarrow \begin{cases} 12 & \text{if } i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2) \\ 3 & \text{if } i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2) \end{cases}$$

end for

end procedure

output: The labeled vertices of $A(Q_m)$ graph.

Now the induced edge labels are as follows:

For $i = 0$ to $m - 1$

Case (i): If $i \equiv 0(\text{mod } 2)$; $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 2$.

Case (ii): If $i \equiv 1(\text{mod } 2)$; $f^*(u_i u_{i+1}) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(u_{i+1})]_2) = 6$.

For $i = 0$ to $\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor - 1$; $f^*(u_{2i+1} v_i) = hd([f(u_{2i+1})]_2, [f(v_i)]_2) = 4$.

$f^*(v_i w_i) = hd([f(u_i)]_2, [f(w_i)]_2) = 2$; $f^*(w_i u_{2i+2}) = hd([f(w_i)]_2, [f(u_{2i+2})]_2) = 4$.

From all the above cases, all the adjacent edges receive distinct even numbers as labels. Hence the Alternate Quadrilateral Snake graph $A(Q_m)$, admits even hamming distance labeling and the even hamming distance number is $\eta''_{hd}(A(Q_m)) = 6, m \geq 2$.

Figure 7: Even Hamming Distance Labeled $A(T_6)$ graph

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proved the existence of the even hamming distance labeling of some snake related graphs and their even hamming distance number were obtained.

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